

A Feasibility Analysis of Tether Localisation for Mobile Robots

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Abstract—The aim of this research is to investigate if tethered robots can be localised using sensors mounted along the tether, also known as tether localisation. For environments where external infrastructure is not available for absolute positioning and conventional SLAM technologies do not work, tether localisation may be able to provide an estimation of position. An example of such an environment is the primary containment vessel (PCV) in reactor 1F at the Fukushima Daiichi Power Plant in Japan. Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) inspections are necessary to allow for the safe decommissioning of the facility. However, external beacons cannot be installed for absolute positioning and the water is too dark and turbid to allow for vision SLAM. This paper presents the work conducted on tether localisation in a 2D plane in order to see if it is viable to estimate the end position of a tether using low-cost commercially viable sensors. Extrapolating the uncertainties observed during experimental testing, it was estimated that for a 30 m tether deployed along the y-axis in a 2D plane, the average absolute error in the position would be (2.79 m, 0.01 m) with an uncertainty of $\pm(3.00 \text{ m}, 9.68 \text{ m})$. This is far greater than the mm accuracy and 10 cm precision target, indicating that this technology is not suitable for tether localisation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robots are very popular for underwater operations. The majority of these operations are conducted by Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) and Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs). These vehicles are used to carry out numerous physical and sensing tasks in a wide array of applications. Specifically, ROVs and AUVs have been used to aid in fossil fuel exploration, geophysical field surveys, salvage operations, offshore exploration [1], [2], [3], [4] and nuclear decommissioning inspection [5]. This means that data can be collected from the environment without having any person exposed to the risks of the environment. In the majority of these operations and tasks, the precise location of the robot is necessary for the robot's autonomous behaviour, accurate characterisation of the environment and the completion of the operation [4], [6], [7]. Traditionally, robots in outdoor environments such as drones or field robots use an absolute positioning system such as the Global Positioning System (GPS). However, for environments that

are GPS denied, robots will use simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) to localise themselves [8].

There are environments where neither absolute positioning systems nor SLAM systems are suitable, such as dark, featureless confined spaces or environments where traditional sensors such as Lidars or sonars aren't effective. The question then arises as to how does one localise a robot in these said environments? An example of one of these environments is the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear plant, where its reactors were damaged during an earthquake in 2011 and were stabilised by flooding them. The extent of the damage that was caused to the reactors is still under investigation. As part of the decommissioning process, ROVs were used to retrieve images of the damage inside of the reactor. The reactor has a 150 mm access port which limits the size of robots and equipment that can be deployed into the environment. The navigation of the ROVs was done via video feedback as no underwater localisation system that currently exists can function in these environments. There are many characteristics of the environment which makes absolute positioning systems and SLAM systems unusable. A review into why these systems are unusable is given by Watson et al. [9]. Hence, the localisation of underwater vehicles is still the subject of a large amount of research [10], [11]. Therefore, a method to localise a robot in said environments is necessary in order for them to complete assigned tasks (such as autonomous surveillance). Due to the access constraints, the localisation system should not require any equipment to be added to the environment for it to work as it would be difficult to place and calibrate them in the environment.

Tethers are used for robots in nuclear environments for multiple reasons, such as: providing power to the robot and retrieval of the robot if it no longer functions, runs out of power or gets stuck in the environment [12], [13], [14]. Additionally, the tether provides a communication link enabling teleoperation of the robot in environments where wireless signals are insufficient or may not work [15].

However, tethers can be problematic as they reduce the manoeuvrability of the robot [16], which causes a problem in unknown, potentially cluttered environments common in nuclear power plants such as Fukushima. The tether can get tangled on many obstacles and thus limit the robots movements. However, a tether is still considered a necessity in these types of environments due to the need to be able to retrieve the robot if it fails. Consequently, a localisation system that uses the tether is seen as preferable for AUVs and ROVs in these unknown, radioactive environments.

In this paper, Section II focuses on the state of the art tether localisation systems. Section III investigates the proposed in air 2D plane localisation system and analyses the results obtained from it. Finally, Section IV concludes this work and outlines the required future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

It is clear that for complex and cluttered environments where additional external infrastructure cannot be used and where there is dark and turbid water with no salient features, there is no suitable localisation technology. Localisation using sensors mounted on the tether is therefore an interesting topic to explore in further detail.

KCF technologies have designed a Smart Tether which has sensor nodes embedded in the tether itself [17] and thus would not require any extra equipment to be installed in the environment. The nodes are used to measure the orientation of the tether and use that information to estimate the position of the robot and the shape of the tether [17]. The system has an accuracy of 1.5 m and in theory be deployed in Fukushima. However, it is too inaccurate to provide a functional navigation system in a confined environment.

The tethered SLAM (TSLAM) approach uses odometry techniques and anchor points around the environment to estimate the position of the robot [18]. The odometry of underwater robotics can be obtained either by using IMUs (Inertial Measurement Unit) or visual odometry which uses stereo cameras. As mentioned, the problem with these two systems is that stereo cameras will not work in dark and turbid water and the IMUs accuracy will decrease over time due to drift. More accurate fibre-optic IMUs are available, however they can be very expensive and relatively large [9].

Multiple companies and universities have experimented with using fibre optics to measure the three dimensional shape or location of an object. Luna Innovations' position-sensing technology is based on Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometry [19]. They experimented with a 30 m fibre optic cable and the accuracy of the measurement was approximately 1% of the length of the tether, at 0.2 Hz [19]. In one of the shape testing demonstrations, the RMS path measurement error was approximately 7.7 cm and a maximum measurement error of 13.5 cm was found. NASA have used

low reflectance Fibre Bragg Gratings (FBG) and strain sensors in a multi-core fibre to provide much more accurate results in a 10 m tether, where NASA claims that their positional accuracy is (less than 1 mm) ten times better than any other comparable fibre based techniques [20]. The characteristics of FBGs change depending on curvature, by sensing the relative change in three or more fibre cores, an accurate change in 3D position can be determined.

In conclusion, there exists many tether localisation systems. In particular, the FBG solution is very promising as it allows for very accurate localisation of the robot compared to the other methods and it can be easily embedded into the tether. However, due to the lack of available publications and the high cost of optical interrogators, alternative more cost effective solutions will be investigated.

III. 2D LOCALISATION SYSTEM

A 3D localisation system is the requirement for real-world underwater deployment. However, to simplify the problem, the first step is to implement a 2D air localisation system, as it makes the validation and experiments feasible. This can then be analysed to see the feasibility of extending the system into a 3D localisation system that can be used underwater.

A. Sensor Selection

To develop a tether localisation system that estimates the end position of the tether, sensors have to be used to measure either the end position of the tether or the physical changes along the tether. By knowing the bends at different points along the tether, it is possible to estimate the end position of it. A 2D localisation system will only require the bend along one axis to be measured. There exists very few options for measuring the the physical changes along a tether. The choices that are currently available are: flex sensors, strain gauges and FBGs, the latter of have been excluded from the research due to thier high cost and lack of published results.

The objective of the tether localisation system is to estimate the end point of a 30 m tether, this implies that there needs to be a large number of sensors on the tether to get an accurate result. However, due to the added weight and difficulties in obtaining measurements from all the sensors along the tether, the number of sensors that can be attached to the tether is limited. Therefore, the sensors must be of adequate length to obtain measurements from the majority of the tether while also minimising the length of the tether without a sensor node. Thus, long sensors are the only viable option.

Flex sensors and strain gauges work in a very similar manner. Long strain gauges are relatively expensive and their behaviour for large deflections is unknown. Therefore, flex sensors were chosen for the prototyping stage of the localisation system. Flex sensors only provide a linear relationship between the bend and resistance in one direction, therefore for a 2D localisation system two flex sensors are required to

measure both directions of the bend. The sensor has a linear relationship between the resistance and the bend angle. The angle that the sensor will read is the angle made by the active length of the sensor, which can be looked at as an arc of a circle, as you can see in Figure 1. This allows for geometry to be used to estimate the end position of each sensor.

Fig. 1. Picture illustrating how the flex sensor works.

B. Theory for the Tether Localisation System

The angle that is read by the sensor is the central angle of the arc. The only known parameter is the active length of the sensor (i.e the arc length L). Figure 2 shows an illustration of the flex sensor (thick line) and all the corresponding parameters that are known or can be derived from known parameters, such as the radius of the circle (r), the chord length (c) and the local coordinates of the end point of the sensor (x_p, y_p). The radius of the circle can be calculated by

Fig. 2. Picture illustrating the flex sensor approach.

the following equation (θ is in radians):

$$r = L/\theta \quad (1)$$

Once the radius is known it is possible to calculate the length of the chord using the cosine rule:

$$c = \sqrt{2r^2(1 - \cos(\theta))} \quad (2)$$

An issue arises when the angle measured by the sensor is 0° , this means that r is undefined. Therefore, an exception was given when $\theta = 0^\circ$, the radius value is not calculated and the chord of the circle is the active length of the sensor i.e. $c = L$.

Since the chord of the circle creates an isosceles triangle, the angle that the chord (c) makes with respect to the y -axis in the local frame can be calculated using:

$$\alpha = \theta/2 \quad (3a)$$

Since:

$$\beta + \alpha = \pi/2 \quad \text{and} \quad \theta + 2\beta = \pi \quad (3b)$$

That then allows for the x and y position of the end point of the sensor to be calculated using trigonometry:

$$x_p = c \sin(\alpha) \quad \text{and} \quad y_p = c \cos(\alpha) \quad (4)$$

The previous steps mention how to get the position of the end point of the sensor in the local frame. However, since the aim of this approach is to localise the end point of the entire tether and not just one sensor, they must be daisy chained together. Figure 3 shows an illustration of the approach of having multiple sensors one after another, where r_n is the radius of the n^{th} sensor and (x_{pn}, y_{pn}) are the positions of the end point of the n^{th} sensor. The shape between sensors 0 and 1 shown in Figure 3 is unlikely to happen in reality. However, it was drawn like this to illustrate the parameters.

Fig. 3. Picture illustrating multiple flex sensor approach.

These are the positions of the end point in the local frame and must be converted in respect to the original frame. To simplify the problem, the y -axis of the local frame is assumed to always be a tangent to the segment of the circle that is created by the flex sensor. Additionally, the y -axis of the sensor is assumed to be at the same angle as the chord of the previous sensor. These assumptions allow for the homogeneous transformation matrices (shown in Equation 5) to be used to transform the local-frame coordinates relative to the starting frame.

$$H_n = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(-\alpha_n) & -\sin(-\alpha_n) & x_{pn} \\ \sin(-\alpha_n) & \cos(-\alpha_n) & y_{pn} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Where α_n is the clockwise rotation of the axis, given by equation 3a (it is negative as it is a clockwise rotation), and x_{pn} and y_{pn} are the x and y position of the origin of the next local frame. To get the position of the end point, the Homogeneous transformation matrix must be multiplied in the correct order as follows:

$$G = H_0 \cdot H_1 \cdot \dots \cdot H_{n-1} \cdot P_n \quad (6)$$

Where G is the position of the end point relative to the starting frame, H_n is the respective Homogeneous transformation matrix and P_n is the position of the end point in the final frame, i.e:

$$P_n = \begin{bmatrix} x_{pn} \\ y_{pn} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

C. Sensor separation

In reality it is not possible to have a large number of sensors along the tether. For a 30 m tether and an active length of 5.357 cm for each sensor, there would be approximately 541 sensors placed along the tether, which is difficult to maintain. Therefore, the sensors must have a separation distance between them. This separation will lead to an error in the final estimated position, as their behaviour will have to be approximated. There are four methods to deal with the separation.

One method is to assume that the separation following each sensor is a continuation of the arc of the circle at the corresponding sensor. The chord of the circle is from the beginning of the sensor to the beginning point of the following sensor, as seen in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Picture illustrating method 1.

The second method is to assume that the separation (s) between sensors is straight and as an extension of the chord, as seen in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Picture illustrating method 2.

The third method is to assume that the sensor separation is straight and a continuation of the trajectory of the tip of the sensor (not the arc of the circle). Figure 6 shows an

illustration of the assumption.

The final method is to assume that the sensor separation is straight and at an angle that is an average between the previous and the following sensor's readings. Figure 6 can also be used to show the illustration of the assumption where in this case $\varphi_1 = \frac{\alpha_0 + \alpha_2}{2}$.

Fig. 6. Picture illustrating methods 3 & 4.

To simplify the calculations, the sensor separation will be considered as a new frame. This frame will be rotated at an angle of φ . Additionally, the next sensor's frame is no longer considered to be the same angle as the chord of the previous sensor, as the new rotation due to the sensor separation needs to be considered. The y -axis of the following sensor's frame, will have the same angle as the sensor separation as illustrated in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Picture illustrating the sensor separation as an additional frame.

Furthermore, the angle of the deployment for the tether must be known so that a rotation matrix can be used to give the position of the end point of the first sensor relative to a pre-set frame. Therefore, for the test rig, the first sensor was fixed approximately vertically to avoid any issues measuring the deployment angle and then converting that to the pre-set frame.

D. Experiment and Analysis of Results

To validate the proposed method a small test rig was built. Three flex sensors were placed on a 30 cm tether to provide the bend angles at different points. Figure 8 shows the rig,

where the start and end points are pinned onto a cm grid. Additionally, the first section of the tether from (0,0) to the

Fig. 8. Experiment rig with three flex sensor placed along the tether.

beginning of the first sensor, is a 7.2 cm vertical piece which is added into the model as a homogeneous transformation with a rotation of 0° and a transformation of $(0, 7.2)$ cm. The location of the next sections of the tether will be done by one of the above mentioned methods. Each method mentioned in the previous section will provide different results. To see how they differ, the tether was moved between two known end points $(15, 20)$ cm and $(15, 17)$ cm repeatedly and the sensor measurements were logged. Figures 9 and 10 show the results from the experiments for the position estimation of $(15, 20)$ cm and $(15, 17)$ cm respectively. The error bars are the standard deviations of the estimated x (horizontal error bar) and y positions (vertical error bar).

Fig. 9. Estimated end position when the end point is $(15, 20)$ cm.

For the position $(15, 20)$ cm method 3 provided the most accurate position estimation with an absolute error of $(0.18, 0.43)$ cm. Whereas for position $(15, 17)$ cm, method 1 provided the most accurate position estimation of the tether with an absolute error of $(0.36, 1.32)$ cm. The average angles measured imply that when the angles are small, method 3

Fig. 10. Estimated end position when the end point is $(15, 17)$ cm.

provides the best solution, whereas when the angles are large method 1 provides the best solution. In practice, both methods can be combined where the estimator can process small angles using method 3 and large angles using method 1.

Method 4 compared to method 3 was more precise, however it was inaccurate in comparison. Additionally, method 2 provided the most precise estimations, however it was the least accurate. The results shown in this section are for a 30 cm tether, if the system is expanded to any tether of a longer length, the estimations are expected to be less accurate and precise.

Furthermore, the assumption that the sensor separation is straight in methods 2, 3 and 4 provides another source of error for the model. A possibility to increase the accuracy and confidence in the result is to ensure that the separations are forced to remain straight by adding a sheathing around them. This however, will affect the manoeuvrability of the robot but it might provide more accurate results as it will limit the sections between sensors from bending. Additionally, in the model, it is assumed that the sensors bend around their middle point, where in reality this bend can start at any part of the sensor.

E. Challenges with proposed System

The proposed system while theoretically possible has too many downfalls, difficulties and areas of added inaccuracy to be investigated further. There were several challenges associated with the model and the chosen sensors. Flex sensors are unreliable as they will not always give the same value for the same bend and their value fluctuates a lot even when held stationary. To help account for this issue, the average of 20 values was used to obtain the measurements used for the experiment.

There is no method for knowing the starting point of the bend on the sensor. This is an issue as it gives varying bend angles which affects the results. Furthermore, if the sensors experience any torsion, their resistance value will change and this leads to further inaccuracies in the estimated

final position. To get the readings from all the sensors across the tether, microcontrollers will need to be placed along the tether. These microcontrollers will require some power to operate and this needs to be considered when choosing the appropriate power supply and whether it will be possible to power all of them simultaneously along the tether. Additionally, the communication between sensor nodes needs to be investigated. If one node fails, it will be really difficult to account for and hence the accuracy of the system will be affected. Furthermore, the extra components and wires on the tether will increase the weight of the tether, which might affect the movement of the robot. Therefore, careful consideration has to be made in order to make sure that the tether is neutrally buoyant after all of this added mass.

The separation between sensors cause an inaccuracy in the estimated end position and when expanding this system to a much a longer tether, these errors will add up significantly. Furthermore, the length of the sensor separations will greatly affect the accuracy of the system. It was estimated that for a 30 m tether, if there was a mere 0.3° estimation error due to the sensor separation, the mean square error in the position estimation is approximately $4000 m^2$. Due to all the mentioned challenges with the system, it is not recommended to further investigate this solution. In order to reach the target accuracy, it is estimated that the sensors should have an uncertainty of $\pm 0.02^\circ$ as that will provide an average absolute error of (0.78, 0.28) mm and an uncertainty of $\pm(100, 0)$ mm. This uncertainty is only achievable by the FBG sensors and therefore, that solution should be further investigated.

IV. CONCLUSION

In order to explain the requirement of a tether localisation system, a summary of the current underwater localisation systems was discussed. Additionally, tether localisation systems were summarised and it was concluded that they were either inaccurate or expensive. Therefore, a cost effective system was explored. The suggested localisation method required sensors to measure characteristics along the tether to estimate the end position of the tether. The possible sensors were discussed and the flex sensors were chosen. Knowing how the sensor works and with a few assumptions to simplify the problem, it was possible to come up with an algorithm to estimate the end position of the tether.

Four methods were considered to estimate the behaviour of the tether in the sections without a sensor, two of which provided accurate results for different end points. It was concluded that this system should no longer be considered and researched due to the build up of error throughout the system and the many issues that will come up when expanding the system to a longer tether. The main issue with the system was the low accuracy of the flex sensors. Therefore, better sensors need to be investigated. The error propagation along a 30 m tether suggests that the target accuracy of the sensors along the tether should be $\pm 0.02^\circ$, which is attainable by FBG sensors.

However, more research is required to test its capabilities and limitations.

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